

Index of Training material

Building the future of bioinformatics with Nextflow: Technical innovation, community engagement, and career development opportunities

19 Month 2024

Material Name	Material Type (Format)	Description	URL/Persistent Identifier
Building the future of bioinformatics with Nextflow: Technical innovation, community engagement, and career development opportunities	Recording (YouTube video)	Recording of the live webinar presentation	Available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yYoo6ZrVk4w
2024-09-19_Australian-BioCommons-Webinar_GVdAuwera	Slides (PDF)	PDF copy of the slides presented during the webinar	Included in this Zenodo record